

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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DYNAMICS OF PROSTHETIC STOMATITIS AND ORAL HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE AFTER PROSTHETIC TREATMENT**Rasulova M.M., Saidov A.A.**

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Resume. *Acrylic-based removable dentures are a significant factor in the development of denture (prosthetic) stomatitis — chronic atrophic candidiasis — and reduce oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL). This prospective study examined the dynamics of prosthetic-stomatitis indicators and OHRQoL during prosthetic treatment of partial and complete edentulism with conventional and contemporary dentures, before treatment and at subsequent stages. Mucosal status was assessed by the Newton classification and dental parameters, the microflora (including Candida albicans) and quality of life by the OHIP-14 questionnaire, with a healthy control group for comparison. After treatment, mucosal inflammation, Candida counts and the OHIP-14 score decreased significantly in all groups. Although baseline impairment was more pronounced in complete edentulism, the relative improvement was greater; the conventional and contemporary methods converged in their final outcome, and patients' indicators approached the control values.*

Key words: *prosthetic stomatitis, oral health-related quality of life, OHIP-14, Candida albicans, Newton classification, partial edentulism, complete edentulism.*

ПРОТЕЗ СТОМАТИТИ ВА ОҒИЗ БЎШЛИҒИ САЛОМАТЛИГИ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ҲАЁТ СИФАТИНИНГ ОРТОПЕДИК ДАВОЛАШДАН КЕЙИНГИ ДИНАМИКАСИ**Расулова М.М., Саидов А.А.**

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Резюме. *Акрил асосидаги олинадиган протезлар протез стоматити (сурункали атрофик кандидоз) ривожланишида муҳим омил бўлиб, оғиз бўшлиғи саломатлиги билан боғлиқ ҳаёт сифатини (ОБСБҲС) пасайтиради. Ушбу проспектив тадқиқотда қисман ва тўлиқ тишсизликни анъанавий ва замонавий протезлар билан ортопедик даволаш жараёнида протез стоматити белгилари ва ОБСБҲС динамикаси даволашдан олдин ва ундан кейинги босқичларда ўрганилди. Шиллиқ қават ҳолати Ньютон таснифи ва стоматологик параметрлар, оғиз микрофлораси (жумладан Candida albicans) ҳамда OHIP-14 сўровномаси ёрдамида баҳоланди; қиёс учун соғлом назорат гуруҳи шакллантирилди. Даволашдан сўнг барча гуруҳларда шиллиқ қават яллиғланиши, Candida миқдори ва OHIP-14 кўрсаткичи ишончли пасайди. Тўлиқ тишсизликда бошланғич бузилиш оғирроқ бўлса-да, нисбий яхшиланиш юқорироқ бўлди; анъанавий ва замонавий усуллар якуний натижа бўйича бир-бирига яқинлашди ва беморлар кўрсаткичлари назорат гуруҳи қийматларига етди.*

Калим сўзлар: *протез стоматити, оғиз бўшлиғи саломатлиги билан боғлиқ ҳаёт сифати, OHIP-14, Candida albicans, Ньютон таснифи, қисман тишсизлик, тўлиқ тишсизлик.*

ДИНАМИКА ПРОТЕЗНОГО СТОМАТИТА И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ, СВЯЗАННОГО СО ЗДОРОВЬЕМ ПОЛОСТИ РТА, ПОСЛЕ ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ**Расулова М.М., Саидов А.А.**

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Резюме. *Съёмные протезы на основе акрила являются значимым фактором развития протезного стоматита (хронического атрофического кандидоза) и снижают качество жизни, связанное со здоровьем полости рта (КЖЗПР). В настоящем проспективном исследовании изучена динамика признаков протезного стоматита и КЖЗПР при ортопедическом лечении частичной и полной адентии традиционными и современными протезами — до лечения и на последующих этапах. Состояние слизистой оценивали по классификации Ньютона и стоматологическим параметрам, микрофлору (включая Candida albicans) и качество жизни — по опроснику OHIP-14; для сравнения сформирована здоровая контрольная группа. После лечения во всех группах достоверно снижались воспаление слизистой, количество Candida и балл OHIP-14. При полной адентии исходные нарушения были более выраженными, однако относительное улучшение оказалось большим; традиционный и современный методы сблизились по итоговому результату, а показатели пациентов приблизились к значениям контрольной группы.*

Ключевые слова: протезный стоматит, качество жизни, связанное со здоровьем полости рта, OHIP-14, *Candida albicans*, классификация Ньютона, частичная адентия, полная адентия.

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Acrylic (plastic)-based removable dentures are widely used to compensate for tooth loss (edentulism) owing to their low cost, ease of fabrication and repair, and esthetic properties. However, the roughness of the acrylic resin surface, its relatively low mechanical strength, and the constant pressure of the denture on the mucosa create the basis for a number of complications [1, 5]. The most common complication of removable denture use is denture stomatitis, i.e., chronic atrophic candidiasis, which is the most prevalent chronic inflammatory condition in patients who wear dentures; according to various sources, its prevalence ranges from 20–67% [1, 5]. This condition is observed in both partial and complete edentulism and occurs more frequently with acrylic dentures than with other materials [5]. Its etiology is multifactorial: mechanical trauma, inadequate hygiene, and — most importantly — colonization by *Candida albicans*, the fungus adhering to the acrylic resin surface and forming a biofilm [2, 6]. The clinical severity is divided into three types according to the Newton classification: I — pinpoint hyperemia, II — diffuse erythema, III — granular hyperplasia [1]. Denture stomatitis is accompanied by pain and discomfort and reduces the patient's oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL) [3]. Oral health-related quality of life is most often assessed with the Oral Health Impact Profile and its compact 14-item version (OHIP-14), which today are among the most widely used instruments and show high sensitivity to changes in prosthetic and mucosal conditions [3, 8].

In the prosthetic treatment of edentulism, the choice of method — from conventional (classic acrylic-base) constructions to solutions based on contemporary materials — is a subject of ongoing debate [9, 10]. However, the dynamics over time of denture-stomatitis indicators (clinical and microbiological) and of quality of life, especially comparing partial and complete edentulism and in the context of conventional and contemporary methods, are rarely studied in an integrated manner [7, 8]. The scientific novelty of this study is that the changes in denture stomatitis and OHRQoL are analyzed not as a static "before–after" but as a continuous dynamic across four time points, examining clinical, microbiological, and subjective indicators in their interrelation and in comparison with a healthy control group.

Aim of the study. To comparatively assess, at four time points, the dynamics of denture-stomatitis indicators (Newton classification, clinical parameters, oral microflora) and oral health-related quality of life (OHIP-14) during the treatment of partial and complete edentulism with conventional and contemporary prosthetic methods; to determine the relationship between clinical-microbiological recovery and the OHIP-14 score; and to compare the results with the values of a healthy control group.

Materials and methods. The study was organized as a prospective, dynamic observation. It enrolled 131 patients who received prosthetic treatment for a diagnosis of edentulism of varying degrees. The patients were divided into four groups by type of diagnosis (partial edentulism — 91; complete edentulism — 40) and treatment method (conventional — 62; contemporary — 69). For comparative assessment, a control group of 22 individuals with relatively healthy oral mucosa was formed (Table 1). All indicators were recorded at four time points — before treatment and 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months afterwards.

Table 1.

General characteristics of the study groups

Group	Diagnosis	Treatment method	n	Mean age (M±σ)
1	Partial edentulism	Conventional (acrylic base)	43	53.5±6.4
2	Partial edentulism	Contemporary construction	48	54.1±6.0
3	Complete edentulism	Conventional (acrylic base)	19	68.3±3.1
4	Complete edentulism	Contemporary construction	21	67.1±3.5
Control	Healthy mucosa	—	22	—
Total	—	—	131	—

Note: the partial-edentulism groups are middle-aged, whereas the complete-edentulism groups constitute a relatively older cohort.

The diagnosis of denture stomatitis was made on the basis of clinical examination, and the severity was determined according to the Newton classification (types I–III). A total of 14 dental parameters related to the oral mucosa and the denture were assessed (hyperemia, swelling, erosion, bleeding, signs of atrophy, pain syndrome, hygiene indices, salivary flow rate — SFR, epithelial regeneration rate, pH, and others). The oral microflora was studied by the counts (CFU/ml) of six microorganisms — *Staphylococcus aureus*, Enter-

ococcus faecalis, Streptococcus mutans, Streptococcus salivarius, Candida albicans, and Candida tropicalis. Quality of life was assessed using the OHIP-14 questionnaire (14 items, each scored 0–4; a decrease in the score indicates an improvement in quality of life). In the statistical analysis, the mean (M), standard deviation (σ), and standard error of the mean (m) were calculated. The paired Student's t-test was used to compare within-group pre-treatment and 3-month values, and Welch's t-test for independent samples was used to compare the conventional and contemporary methods. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. Dynamics of the oral microflora. After treatment, the counts of the six microorganisms decreased significantly in all groups (paired t-test, mostly $p < 0.001$). The counts of Candida species — the principal causative agents of denture stomatitis — decreased several hundredfold (Table 2): for example, in the conventional partial-edentulism group C. albicans decreased from 501,140 to 2,215 CFU/ml, and in the contemporary complete-edentulism group from 566,857 to 2,970 CFU/ml. The most pronounced decrease was recorded for the cariogenic S. mutans (~99%).

Table 2.

Dynamics of Candida species counts (CFU/ml) ($M \pm \sigma$; $p < 0.001$ for all)

Group	C. albicans (before)	3 months	C. tropicalis (before)	3 months
Partial · conventional	501,140±278,830	2,215	251,349±150,750	934
Partial · contemporary	474,354±269,457	2,371	238,354±157,216	1,243
Complete · conventional	335,526±245,594	2,910	247,684±143,470	892
Complete · contemporary	566,857±302,791	2,970	204,286±148,293	1,668

Note: the “3 months” column shows the final mean value (CFU/ml). The decrease is statistically significant for all species ($p < 0.001$).

Dynamics of dental (clinical) parameters. The clinical picture improved consistently in all groups: hyperemia, swelling, pain syndrome, and hygiene indices decreased markedly, whereas the SFR, environmental pH, and epithelial regeneration rate increased. The Newton scale, reflecting the severity of denture stomatitis, decreased significantly in all groups (Table 3). For example, in partial edentulism hyperemia decreased from 2.0 to ~0.33–0.35 and pain syndrome from 1.1–1.2 to ~0.04–0.09; in complete edentulism hyperemia decreased from 2.95 to ~0.68–0.71 and pain syndrome from 2.2–2.3 to ~0.43–0.47. The epithelial regeneration rate increased from 8–10 to 12–13 %/day, and the pH neutralized from 6.0–6.2 to ~6.68–6.71.

Table 3.

Dynamics of the Newton scale (denture stomatitis severity) ($M \pm \sigma$)

Group	Before treatment	After 3 months	p^*
Partial · conventional	1.81±0.39	0.74±0.44	<0.001
Partial · contemporary	1.69±0.51	0.65±0.48	<0.001
Complete · conventional	2.89±0.32	0.95±0.52	<0.001
Complete · contemporary	2.71±0.56	0.81±0.51	<0.001
Control group	0.18±0.39	—	—

* — paired Student's t-test (before treatment ↔ 3 months). Baseline severity (Newton types II–III) is higher in complete edentulism.

Quality of life — OHIP-14 dynamics. The mean OHIP-14 score decreased consistently in all groups over the observation period, i.e., quality of life improved steadily (Figure 1). At baseline, the score was 1.9–2.0 in partial edentulism and 3.1–3.2 in complete edentulism. By the end of the three-month observation, the improvement was highly statistically significant in all groups ($p < 0.001$). The relative improvement was 40.0–43.9% in partial edentulism and 51.5% in complete edentulism — although the patients with complete edentulism were in a more severe baseline condition, the relative gain was greater in their group. Relative improvement (Δ) over 3 months: partial conventional 43.9%, partial contemporary 40.0%, complete conventional and contemporary 51.5% (paired Student's t-test, $p < 0.001$ in all groups). The dashed line marks the healthy-control value (1.75; $n=22$). A lower score corresponds to better quality of life. Comparison of conventional and contemporary methods. At the final (three-month) stage of treatment, no statistically significant difference was found between the conventional and contemporary methods in any of the microbiological (6 indicators), clinical (14 parameters), or OHIP-14 measures — all values were ns ($p > 0.05$) (Table 4). The minimal difference in OHIP-14 that existed at baseline in the partial group ($p=0.023$) had disappeared by 3 months.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the mean OHIP-14 score (M±m, 0–4 scale) during prosthetic treatment.

Table 4.

**Comparison of conventional and contemporary methods
(three-month final outcome, Welch's t-test; p-value)**

Indicator	Partial edentulism	Complete edentulism
OHIP-14	0.455 (ns)	0.803 (ns)
<i>C. albicans</i>	0.805 (ns)	0.955 (ns)
<i>C. tropicalis</i>	0.357 (ns)	0.173 (ns)
Clinical parameters (14)	all ns	all ns

Note: in terms of final effectiveness, the two methods become equivalent and show comparable efficacy.

Functional recovery and concordance with the control. After prosthetics, the occlusal (bite) height increased in both groups: mean difference $\Delta \approx 5.5$ mm ($\sim 9.3\%$ increase; partial 5.45 mm, complete 5.60 mm), an effect almost independent of the type of diagnosis. The final three-month indicators of the treated patients approached the values of the healthy control group considerably (Table 5): for example, pH reached ≈ 6.68 – 6.71 in both groups (6.90 in the control), SFR ≈ 0.30 – 0.32 , and the Newton scale ≈ 0.65 – 0.95 (0.18 in the control).

Table 5.

Main reference indicators of the control group (n=22; M±σ)

Indicator	Value (M±σ)	Interpretation
OHIP-14, mean score	1.75±0.05	low = good
Newton scale	0.18±0.39	low = good
Pain syndrome	0.14±0.34	low = good
Oral hygiene index	0.77±0.28	low = good
Epithelial regeneration, %/day	12.23±0.90	high = good
pH	6.90±0.05	close to neutral = good

Note: the control values serve as a conditional norm (reference).

Since denture stomatitis is dominated by pain, burning, and discomfort, the "physical pain" and "psychological discomfort" domains of OHIP-14 are the most affected at baseline and improve most rapidly as mucosal inflammation (hyperemia, pain syndrome, Newton scale) subsides. Although OHIP-14 is a subjective measure, its dynamics ran parallel to objective clinical (Newton) and microbiological (Candida) recovery — showing that the improvement in patient perception reflects real mucosal changes. This confirms the high sensitivity of OHIP-14 and is consistent with international data [3, 4]. The hundredfold decrease in Candida counts indicates that the main pathogenic link of denture stomatitis has been eliminated [6, 7],

which explains the mucosal recovery and the improved quality of life; the convergence of patients' indicators with the healthy control confirms that prosthetic rehabilitation restored oral cavity homeostasis to normal.

Because a complete denture covers a large mucosal area, especially the hard palate, stomatitis runs a more severe course (higher Newton score and baseline OHIP-14); yet the relative improvement was greatest in this group (~51% vs ~40–44%), reflecting the principle that the deeper the defect, the greater the recovery reserve. The most notable result is the absence of a statistically significant difference between the conventional and contemporary methods across all indicators at three months. This does not mean contemporary methods are useless: within three months the outcome is determined mainly by the resolution of inflammation and adaptation to the denture, whereas the potential advantages of contemporary constructions (service life, durability, fewer repeat adjustments) may emerge only over the long term. The method can therefore be selected individually, according to the patient's clinical condition and resources.

Improvement was stepwise, with the greatest change in the first month and continuing to three months — relevant when planning follow-up visits. Limitations include the 3-month observation period, unequal group sizes, and single-center design; the strengths are the combined use of subjective (OHIP-14), clinical, and microbiological criteria together with a healthy control group.

Conclusion. Treatment of partial and complete edentulism with both conventional and contemporary prosthetic methods significantly reduced the clinical (Newton scale, hyperemia, pain syndrome) and microbiological (*Candida albicans/tropicalis* counts) indicators of denture stomatitis and improved oral health-related quality of life ($p < 0.001$ in all groups). The OHIP-14 score declined in parallel with clinical and microbiological recovery, confirming the questionnaire's high sensitivity and the concordance of subjective and objective indicators. Although complete edentulism showed greater baseline impairment, its relative improvement was larger (51.5% vs ~40–44%). At the three-month outcome, the conventional and contemporary methods did not differ significantly in any indicator (all ns, $p > 0.05$), allowing the method to be selected individually. Patients' final values approached those of the healthy control group, making OHIP-14 a recommended instrument for the dynamic monitoring of denture stomatitis treatment.

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